

STUDIES ON THE CIRCULAR DICHROISM AND ROTATORY DISPERSION.
PART III. MEASUREMENT OF ABSORPTION, CIRCULAR DICHROISM
AND ROTATORY DISPERSION OF POTASSIUM VANADYL *d*-TARTRATE

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Potassium vanadyl *d*-tartrate has been prepared and the measurement of absorption, circular dichroism and the rotatory dispersion have been carried out.

This compound has in the visible region two adjoining optically active absorption bands which cannot be well represented by the absorption equations of Kuhn, Kuhn and Braun, Lowry and Hudson and Bielecki and Henri. So these have been represented by the empirical equation developed by the author (*this Journal*, 1947, 24, 461).

The circular dichroism of the two absorption bands are opposite in sign which has also been expressed by the empirical equations of circular dichroism (*loc. cit.*). The dissymmetry factor "g" in the two absorption bands first increases with frequency, then decreases, changes sign, again increases to a maximum and then again decreases.

The rotatory dispersion in the region of absorption cannot be accurately expressed by the equations of Kuhn and Brann and Lowry and Hudson and has been expressed in a more satisfactory manner by means of modified equations of rotatory dispersion in the region of absorption (*loc. cit.*).

In the two preceding papers of this series (Kar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 278; 1947, 24, 117) the author has reported the preparation of ammonium vanadyl *d*-tartrate and measurement of the circular dichroism and rotatory dispersion and the curves of circular dichroism and rotatory dispersion have been analysed. The investigation has now been extended to potassium vanadyl *d*-tartrate and attempts have been made to obtain more accurate results.

EXPERIMENTAL

This salt was prepared by the same method as the ammonium salt was prepared. Ammonium vanadate (meta, 1g.) was suspended in water and boiled with hydrobromic acid, when a blue solution was obtained. *d*-Tartaric acid (1.2 g.) was then added and the solution was evaporated to a small bulk. It was then neutralised with potassium hydroxide and cooled in ice when crystals of potassium vanadyl *d*-tartrate were obtained. These crystals were thoroughly washed for several times with ice-cold water and dried over calcium chloride in a vacuum desiccator. The molecular formula of the complex by Rosenheim and Mong (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1925, 148, 31) is $K_2[(VO)H_2C_4O_6]$.

The reactions may be represented by the following equations:—

The compounds (I) and (II) with potassium hydroxide give potassium salt.

Measurement of Rotation and Ellipticity.—Rotation and ellipticity were measured by means of Bruhat's method (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1930, **47**, 251). The source of light was a point—o—lite lamp of 1000 c. p. and the monochromatic radiations were obtained by passing the light through a monochromator. The extinction coefficient was determined with the help of a König-Martens spectrophotometer which was set initially at 45°.

A known strength of the solution was made in distilled water and as it was unstable in air, it was preserved in a Thunberg tube. The violet solution of the pure crystals is optically active and circularly dichroic. In the visible region it has got two optically active adjacent absorption bands. The circular dichroism of the two bands are opposite in sign so that the curve of circular dichroism cuts the axis of wave-length, while the two maxima of the two absorption bands are on the same side of the axis. The chromophoric groups, which are responsible for the two absorption bands, are under investigation.

Absorption

The extinction coefficients have been calculated by the relation $\epsilon = 2 \log \tan \theta/l$, where θ is the spectrophotometric reading and l is the length in cm., and have been tabulated in Table I and are represented graphically in Fig. 1. The molecular extinction coefficient has not been calculated as the water of crystallisation of the molecule of potassium vanadyl *d*-tartrate is not known to us. The first absorption band is reduced to a "step out", the maximum of which is very difficult to ascertain, while the second absorption band shows a maximum at about 5150Å. Attempts have therefore been made to analyse the second absorption band only.

Analysis of the Second Absorption Curve.—The following equations have been used to analyse the absorption curve.

(a) Equation of Kuhn (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1929, **B4**, 14; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, **26**, 293) namely,

$$\epsilon = \epsilon_{\max} \frac{\nu^2 \nu'^2}{(\nu_0^2 - \nu^2)^2 + \nu^2 \nu'^2} \approx \epsilon_{\max} \frac{\nu^2}{4(\nu_0 - \nu)^2 + \nu'^2},$$

where ϵ = extinction coefficient at frequency ν , $\epsilon_{\max}$ = maximum extinction coefficient at frequency ν_0 , ν_0 = frequency corresponding to head of the band, ν' = frequency interval between the points at which ϵ is half $\epsilon_{\max}$ which is obtained from the experimental curve of absorption.

(b) Equation of Kuhn and Braun (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930, **B6**, 281) namely

$$\epsilon = \epsilon_{\max} e^{-\left(\frac{\nu_0 - \nu}{\theta}\right)^2}$$

where $\nu' = 1.6651\theta$.

(c) Equation of Lowry and Hudson (*Phil. Trans.*, 1933, **A232**, 117),

$$\epsilon = \epsilon_{\max} e^{-\left[\frac{\nu_0}{\nu} \left(\frac{\nu_0 - \nu}{\theta}\right)\right]^2}$$

(d) Equation suggested by Bielecki and Henri (*Physikal. Z.*, 1913, **14**, 516) is

$$\epsilon = \epsilon_{\max} \frac{\nu}{\nu_0} e^{-\beta(\nu_0 - \nu)^2}$$

where β = a constant embodying the half-width of the band. This equation differs from that proposed by Kuhn and Braun only in the insertion of the factor ν/ν_0 . The values of $\epsilon_{\max}$, $\nu_0\nu'$ and θ , as used in the above equations, are tabulated in Table II. The extinction coefficients calculated from these four equations are tabulated in Table I and graphically represented in Fig. 1. It should be noted that none of the calculated absorption curves represent the experimental data satisfactorily where extinction coefficient is plotted against frequency.

FIG. 1

Analysis of the second absorption band of potassium vanadyl d-lartrate.

1. ————— Experimental curve.
 2. - - - - - Curve calculated from equation (a) of Kuhn.
 3. ······· Curve calculated from equation (b) of Kuhn and Braun.
 4. - · - · - · Curve calculated from equation (c) of Lowry and Hudson.
 5. - - - - - Curve calculated from equation (d) of Bielecki and Henri.
 6. - · - · - · Curve calculated from our equation.

In order to represent the characteristic feature of the experimental curve the modified absorption equations (Kar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **25**, 461) have been used, namely

$$\epsilon = \epsilon_{\max} e^{-\left(\frac{\nu_0 - \nu}{\theta_1}\right)^2}$$

for extinction coefficients on the low frequency side and

$$\epsilon = \epsilon_{\max} e^{-\left(\frac{\nu - \nu_0}{\theta_2}\right)^2}$$

for extinction coefficients on the high frequency side, where the parameters θ_1 and θ_2 are defined by the following equations :

$$\theta_1 = \frac{\nu_0 - \nu_1}{0.8326} \quad \text{and} \quad \theta_2 = \frac{\nu_2 - \nu_0}{0.8326},$$

ν_1 and ν_2 are the frequencies on the long wave-length side and short wave-length side of $\epsilon_{\max}$ respectively, of the points at which ϵ is half $\epsilon_{\max}$.

The parameters of the new equations θ_1 and θ_2 in the case of potassium vanadyl *d*-tartrate are also set out in Table II and the calculated extinction coefficients are tabulated in Table I and graphically represented in Fig. 1. It is interesting to note that the agreement between the experimental and theoretical data is now better than any of the previous equations and is well within the limits of experimental error.

TABLE I

$c = 5.625 \text{ g./100 c.c.}$ $l = 5 \text{ mm.}$ $t = 30^\circ.$

First absorption band.

$\nu \times 10^{-14}$	...	4.470	4.559	4.711	4.839	4.999	5.091
$\epsilon_{\text{obs.}}$	...	1.209	1.365	1.405	1.447	1.488	1.618

Second absorption band.

$\nu \times 10^{-14}$	$\epsilon_{\text{obs.}}$	$\epsilon_{\text{calc.}}$				
		(a) Kuhn	(b) K & B.	(c) L & H.	(d) B & H.	(e) Kar.
5.193	1.756	1.371	1.425	1.245	1.272	1.666
5.266	1.852	1.515	1.599	1.459	1.447	1.807
5.493	2.17	1.998	2.088	2.052	1.972	2.180
5.607	2.288	2.216	2.269	2.257	2.185	2.31
5.759	2.349	2.393	2.397	2.397	2.373	2.398
5.820	2.413					
5.898	2.349	2.382	2.391	2.391	2.423	2.380
6.250	1.447	1.776	1.881	1.945	2.021	1.646
6.413	1.134	1.435	1.506	1.636	1.660	1.168
6.884	0.213 ?	0.757	0.5309	0.8162	0.6281	0.2339

TABLE II

Parameters of second absorption band.

λ_0	$\nu_0 \times 10^{-14}$	$\epsilon_{\max}$	$\nu \times 10^{-14}$	$\theta \times 10^{-14}$	$\nu_1 \times 10^{-14}$	$\theta_1 \times 10^{-14}$	$\nu_2 \times 10^{-14}$	$\theta_2 \times 10^{-14}$
5153 Å	5.82	2.41	1.44	0.865	4.96	1.033	6.4	0.6966

Circular Dichroism

Measurement of ellipticity was carried out in both the absorption bands and these were found to be opposite in sign. From the ellipticity circular dichroism was calculated by the relation

$$(\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r) = \frac{4 \log_{10} e \phi}{l}$$

were ϵ_l and ϵ_r are the extinction coefficients for l and r light, l is the length of the solution in cm., ϕ is the ellipticity expressed in radians. If ϕ is expressed in degrees, we have

$$(\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r) = \frac{4 \times 0.4343 \times \phi}{57.296 \times l}$$

FIG. 2

Circular dichroism of potassium vanadyl d-tartrate,

- 1. ——— Experimental curve.
- 2. Theoretical circular dichroism curve.
- 3. ——— Dissymmetry factor— g .

These observed values of $(\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r)$ are given in Table III against the respective frequencies. The experimental curve of circular dichroism for both the bands is represented in Fig 2. The dissymmetry factor $g = (\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r)/\epsilon$ is tabulated in Table III and is also shown in the same figure. It should be noted that the dissymmetry factor, g_r first increases with increase of frequency, then decreases, changes sign and again increases to a maximum and then again decreases. The distance of separation of the two coupled electrons, according to Born's theory of electronic vibrators and Kufin's molecular model, is also calculated by the relation

$$g_v = \frac{2\pi d}{\lambda_0} \text{ or } d = \frac{g_v \lambda_0}{2\pi}$$

and found to be equal to 54×10^{-8} cm. in the first absorption band and 41×10^{-8} in the second absorption band.

Analysis of the Curves of Circular Dichroism.—It has already been shown that the

experimental absorption curve can be represented very closely by means of the new equations

$\epsilon = \epsilon_{\max} e^{-\left(\frac{\nu_0 - \nu}{\theta_1}\right)^2}$ for frequencies less than ν_0 and $\epsilon = \epsilon_{\max} e^{-\left(\frac{\nu - \nu_0}{\theta_2}\right)^2}$ for frequencies greater than ν_0 . Similarly, circular dichroism can also be represented to a very close approximation by the expressions

$$(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2) = (\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)_{\max} e^{-\left(\frac{\nu_0 - \nu}{\theta_1}\right)^2} \text{ for frequencies less than } \nu_0 \text{ and}$$

$$(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2) = (\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)_{\max} e^{-\left(\frac{\nu - \nu_0}{\theta_2}\right)^2} \text{ for frequencies greater than } \nu_0,$$

where ν_0 is the frequency corresponding to maximum circular dichroism $(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)_{\max}$ and $\theta_1 = \frac{\nu_0 - \nu_1}{0.8320}$ and $\theta_2 = \frac{\nu_2 - \nu_0}{0.8326}$, ν_1 and ν_2 are the frequencies at which $(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)$ is half the maximum value. The values of ν_0 , ν_1 , ν_2 , θ_1 , θ_2 and $(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)_{\max}$, as determined from the experimental curves of circular dichroism are set out in Table IV. The calculated values of $(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)$ according to the above equations and the corresponding curves are given side by side in Table III and in Fig. 2.

Rotatory Dispersion

This work was undertaken with the object of determining the mathematical form of the curve of rotatory dispersion in the region of absorption. The experimental data for the measurement of rotatory dispersion for a concentration of potassium vanadyl *d*-tartrate of 5.625 g./100 c.c. and length of the solution 1 cm. are given in Table V. It may be noted that the usual characteristics of anomalous rotatory dispersion associated with the first absorption band do not appear in our measurements as these all lie towards the longer wave-lengths which have not been investigated.

TABLE III

Pot. vanadyl *d*-tartrate = 5.625 g./100 c.c. $l = 1$ cm. $t = 30^\circ$.

$\nu \times 10^{-14}$.	$(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)_{\text{obs.}}$	$(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)_{\text{calc.}}$	g.	$\nu \times 10^{-14}$.	$(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)_{\text{obs.}}$	$(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)_{\text{calc.}}$	g.
First curve of circular dichroism				Second curve of circular dichroism.			
4.315	-0.038*	-0.038	...	5.193	0.0152	0.0306	0.0086
4.47	-0.0567	-0.0583	-0.0469	5.266	0.0364	0.0418	0.0196
4.659	-0.0727	-0.0748	-0.0533	5.37	0.061*	0.0609	
4.711	-0.0755	-0.07598	-0.0537	5.493	0.0995	0.0835	0.0458
4.72	-0.076*	-0.076	...	5.607	0.1100	0.1059	0.0481
4.839	-0.0649	-0.066	-0.0448	5.759	0.1176	0.1211	0.0501
4.985	-0.038*	-0.038	...	5.8	0.1218*	0.1218	...
4.999	-0.03305	-0.0350	-0.0222	5.82	0.1208	0.1217	0.0501
5.091	-0.0114	-0.0195	-0.00705	5.898	0.1197	0.1191	0.05095
				6.25	0.0756	0.0753	0.0523
				6.34	0.0609*	0.0609	...
				6.473	0.047	0.0498	0.04144

* Interpolated.

TABLE IV

λ_0	$\nu_0 \times 10^{-14}$	$(\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r)_{\max}$	$\nu_1 \times 10^{-14}$	$\theta_1 \times 10^{-14}$	$\nu_2 \times 10^{-14}$	$\theta_2 \times 10^{-14}$	$\theta \times 10^{-14}$
(a) Parameters of first circular dichroism curve							
6356Å	4.72	-0.076	4.315	0.4865	4.985	0.3183	0.4024
(b) Parameters of second circular dichroism curve.							
5172Å	5.8	0.1218	5.37	0.5165	6.34	0.6486	0.5826

These observed rotations for each wave-length, $[\alpha]$, are the algebraic sum of all the partial rotations due to different optically active absorption bands in the visible and ultraviolet regions. These observed values of rotations are represented graphically as curve 1 in Fig. 3.

Analysis of the Curve of Rotatory Dispersion.—The following equations have been used to analyse the curve of rotatory dispersion.

(a) Equation of Kuhn and Braun (*loc. cit.*), namely

$$\alpha = \frac{57.3}{2\sqrt{\pi}} \cdot \frac{(\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r)_{\max}}{\log_{10} e} \cdot \frac{\nu}{\nu_0} \left[e^{-\left(\frac{\nu_0 - \nu}{\theta}\right)^2} \int_0^{\frac{\nu_0 - \nu}{\theta}} e^{x^2} dx - \frac{\theta}{2(\nu_0 + \nu)} \right]$$

where α is the rotatory contribution of an optically active absorption band, expressed in degrees per cm. column of the solution at frequency ν ; ϵ_l, ϵ_r are the extinction coefficients of l and r light and $(\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r)_{\max}$ is the maximum value of the circular dichroism of that band at frequency ν_0 and the parameter θ is related to the half-width of the experimental curve of circular dichroism of the band by the relation $\nu' = 1.6651\theta$. The values of $(\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r)_{\max}$, ν_0 and θ for both the curves of circular dichroism are already given in Table IV. The rotatory contributions at different wave-lengths for each of the absorption bands have been calculated separately.

The algebraic sum of the calculated partial rotations, $[\alpha]_1$, and $[\alpha]_2$, for different wave-lengths of the two optically active absorption bands and the difference between $[\alpha]$ and $[\alpha]_1 + [\alpha]_2$ are given in Table V. This difference evidently represents the residual rotations due to absorption bands in the ultraviolet region. The algebraic sum of the calculated partial rotations and also the residual rotation are represented graphically as curves 2 and 5 in Fig. 3. The difference curve 5 should be normal, that is, the rotation should increase progressively with decreasing wave-lengths in the region of the first and the second absorption bands; but it actually contains two loops, one in the region of first absorption band and the other in the region of second absorption band. These loops may be attributed partly to experimental errors and partly to the fact that the absorption equation of Kuhn and Braun, on the basis of which the above rotation equation has been derived, could not represent the experimental data accurately.

FIG. 3

Rotatory dispersion of potassium vanadyl d-tartrate.

1. Experimental curve.
2. Theoretical curve calculated from the equation of Kuhn and Braun.
3. Theoretical curve calculated from the equation of Lowry and Hudson
4. Theoretical curve calculated from our equation.
5. Difference curve (curve 1 minus curve 2).
6. Difference curve (curve 1 minus curve 3).
7. Difference curve (curve 1 minus curve 4).

(b) Equation of Lowry and Hudson, namely

$$\alpha = \frac{57.3}{2\sqrt{\pi}} \cdot \frac{(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)_{\max}}{\log_{10} e} \cdot \frac{\lambda_0}{\lambda} \left[e^{-\left(\frac{\lambda - \lambda_0}{\theta}\right)^2} \int_0^{\frac{\lambda - \lambda_0}{\theta}} e^{x^2} dx + \frac{\theta}{2(\lambda + \lambda_0)} \right]$$

$$= \frac{57.3}{2\sqrt{\pi}} \cdot \frac{(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)_{\max}}{\log_{10} e} \cdot \frac{\nu}{\nu_0} \left[e^{-\left[\frac{\nu_0}{\nu} \left(\frac{\nu_0 - \nu}{\theta}\right)\right]^2} \int_0^{\frac{\nu_0}{\nu} \left(\frac{\nu_0 - \nu}{\theta}\right)} e^{x^2} dx + \frac{\nu_0}{2\nu_0(\nu_0 + \nu)} \right]$$

The symbols have the same significance and values as before. The algebraic sum of the calculated partial rotations $[\alpha]_1$ and $[\alpha]_2$ and the difference between the observed rotation and this algebraic sum are tabulated in Table V. The algebraic sum of the calculated partial rotations and also the difference are also represented graphically as curve 3 and 6 in Fig. 3. The difference curve 6 shows that the two loops, one in the first absorption

band and the other in the second absorption band, shows no sign of improvement towards disappearance, thus indicating that the absorption equation of Lowry and Hudson, on which the above rotation equation is based, is also inadequate to represent the experimental data accurately.

(c) A third attempt was made to analyse the curve of rotatory dispersion by means of a modified expressions of the same type as that of Kuhn and Braun, based on our new absorption equations and already given in the preceding paper (*loc. cit.*). The equations are

$$\alpha = \frac{57.3}{2\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)_{\max}}{\log_{10} e} \frac{\nu_i}{\nu_0} \left[e^{-\left(\frac{\nu_0 - \nu}{\theta_1}\right)^2} \int_0^{\frac{\nu_0 - \nu}{\theta_1}} e^{-x^2} dx - \frac{\theta_2}{2(\nu_0 + \nu)} \right]$$

for frequencies less than ν_0 , and

$$\alpha = -\frac{57.3}{2\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)_{\max}}{\log_{10} e} \frac{\nu}{\nu_0} \left[e^{-\left(\frac{\nu - \nu_0}{\theta_2}\right)^2} \int_0^{\frac{\nu - \nu_0}{\theta_2}} e^{-x^2} dx + \frac{\theta_1}{2(\nu_0 + \nu)} \right]$$

for frequencies greater than ν_0 .

TABLE V

Conc. of pot. vanadyl d-tartrate = 5.625 g./100 c.c. $l = 1$ cm. $t = 30^\circ$. Observed rotation = $[\alpha] = X$. Algebraic sum of the calculated partial rotation according to different equations = $[\alpha]_1 + [\alpha]_2 = Y$.

λ .	X.	Kuhn & Braun		Lowry & Hudson		Kar	
		Y.	X - Y.	Y.	X - Y.	Y.	X - Y.
6708Å	1.87	-0.44	2.31	-0.67	2.54	-0.42	2.29
6438	2.66	0.67	1.99	0.44	2.22	0.60	2.06
6362	2.87	1.12	1.75	0.88	1.99	0.96	1.91
5893	5.58	3.61	1.97	3.49	2.09	3.38	2.20
5780	5.85	3.71	2.14	3.76	2.09	3.39	2.46
5700	5.80	3.65	2.15	3.83	1.97	3.31	2.49
5461	5.10	2.89	2.21	3.25	1.85	2.74	2.36
5350	4.30	2.16	2.14	2.53	1.77	2.09	2.21
5209	2.60	1.01	1.59	1.35	1.25	0.83	1.77
5153	1.97	0.49	1.48	0.78	1.19	0.28	1.69
5086	1.47	-0.15	1.62	0.15	1.32	-0.28	1.75
4800	0.38	-2.13	2.51	-1.77	2.15	-2.18	2.56
4678	0.25	-2.26	2.51	-2.01	2.26	-2.42	2.67

θ_1 and θ_2 for both the bands have the same values as used in our circular dichroism equations and given in Table IV and the other symbols have the same significance and values as before. The algebraic sum of the calculated partial rotations and the difference between the observed rotation and this sum are also given in Table V and represented graphically as curves 4 and 7 in Fig. 3. The difference curve 7 shows that the two loops, which has to be eliminated, show a sign of improvement, though not disappeared, thus indicating that the above expressions represent the partial rotations of both the bands more accurately than the equation of Kuhn and Braun and of Lowry and Hudson.

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